

EXAMINING INDIA'S MOTIVES FOR CAUSING THE STRATEGIC INSTABILITY IN SOUTH ASIA

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Abstract

Nuclear deterrence aimed to prevent adversaries from planning and organising acts of violence and war, driven by the fear of consequences they could ill afford. Intellectuals during the Cold War also made us believe that the nuclear states would not go to war with each other due to the presence of undefendable atomic weapons. Perhaps the dicta held its ground during the Cold War era due to the establishment of Mutually Assured Destruction (MAD) between the two superpowers, the US and the Soviet Union. However, if the same were to happen in South Asia as well, it would perhaps be too optimistic. India has time and again challenged the establishment of strategic stability and insists that there is a space for war under the nuclear overhang. In doing so, India has made two attempts, in February 2019 and May 2025, to engage Pakistan in violent conflicts, mainly using its air power against Pakistan's counterforce and countervalue targets deep inside Pakistan. Pakistan responded in kind with the requisite means, ably led by the Pakistan Air Force. Deploying deductive reasoning and an explanatory approach, this paper aims to examine India's motives to challenge the dictum that nuclear states do not go to war with each other directly.

INTRODUCTION

States acquire power and develop capabilities to influence other states. For this purpose, the major powers developed nuclear capabilities to influence relatively minor states and concurrently avoid direct military engagements between themselves for fear of Mutually Assured Destruction (MAD). This traditional meaning and concept of deterrence worked well between the Cold War adversaries because they understood its consequences and perhaps learned some lessons after the Cuban Missile Crisis of 1962.ⁱ However, the Cold War principles are valid only for rational people and not for the likes of India's Prime Minister Narendra Modi, who follows a hardline Hindutva Philosophy of his terror outfit, RSS. Modi has converted India into a Hindu State from a well-established secular state. Modi cannot be trusted with nuclear weapons because he has an outright conventional numerical superiority over Pakistan in all domains. Moreover, India under Modi

has made two attempts, in February 2019 and May 2025, where the Indian Air Force (IAF) carried out deep strikes against Pakistan's counterforce and countervalue targets. At the same time, the PAF responded resolutely on both occasions, particularly in May 2025, when it shot down multiple fighter aircraft, including the IAF's mainstay, the French Rafael. Yet, this is a dangerous situation that requires deliberation at all levels to prevent continued instability, both at the strategic and operational levels. This author insists that in the presence of an active dispute between the two neighbouring states, the possibility of military engagement remains with varying degrees of probability. The degree of probability will depend on the evolving international and regional environment, as well as the political will to resolve the dispute by military means of either state.ⁱⁱ

Central Argument

The possibility of yet another military engagement between India and Pakistan, like February 2019 and May 2025, exists with varying degrees of probability, thus challenging the efficacy of nuclear deterrence and strategic stability in South Asia. Therefore, it is necessary to examine India's motives to engage Pakistan in violent conflicts at regular intervals, thus causing strategic instability in the region.

Cold War Rivals versus South Asian Rivals

The concept of deterrence is as old as warfare itself; however, it needs to be understood before it is relied upon as a primary tool for the security of a state. In modern times, the concept and definitions draw reference to the birth of nuclear weapons in 1945. Bernard Brodie, strategist of nuclear deterrence theory, was of the view that "if an aggressor feared retaliation in kind, he would not attack."ⁱⁱⁱ Explaining further, Brodie wrote, "Thus far, the chief purpose of our military establishment has been to win wars. From now on, its chief purpose must be to avert them."^{iv} This traditional meaning and concept of deterrence served its purpose in letter and spirit between the Cold War rivals: the United States (US) and the erstwhile Soviet Union (USSR), because they understood its consequences and perhaps learned some lessons after the Cuban Missile Crisis of 1962. Thereafter, the two superpowers of the time never clashed with each other directly and continued to exercise their military power in wars, conflicts, and crises through proxies.

However, the situation in South Asia regarding nuclear equations appears to be entirely different and quite strange. India and Pakistan have been de facto atomic states since May 1998, when India carried out its second wave of nuclear tests after a gap of nearly 24 years.^v India managed to achieve the surprise, but Pakistan had to face the wrath for the Indian action. The international community launched an assertive campaign to prevent Pakistan from carrying out its nuclear tests to even with India. But Pakistan refused to compromise on its security and carried out five atomic explosions on 28 May 1998, followed by another two days later. Pakistan only tested its capability in response to Indian tests within three weeks, and thus, two South Asian rivals declared themselves nuclear states. Pakistan's nuclear tests, in

response to those of India's, perhaps reduced the strategic imbalance in the region, but placed immense responsibility on its leadership. The Western world, particularly the US, considers South Asia a dangerous place because of frequent wars, conflicts, and crises between India and Pakistan over the disputed territories of J&K. The US and its allies remain overly concerned about the nuclear safety and security issues, particularly for Pakistan. However, Pakistan carries an excellent record of nuclear safety and security.

South Asian situation changed considerably on May 11, 1998, when the Indian Prime Minister Vajpayee proudly announced that India had successfully carried out three nuclear explosions and should be accepted as the sixth NWS.^{vi} India carried out three more nuclear tests on May 13, 1998. Nuclearisation of the Indian armed forces and the annexation of Azad Jammu & Kashmir figured prominently in the BJP's political agenda.⁵ But soon after its triumph in the nuclear field, Indian Home Minister L K Advani openly challenged the Pakistani leadership that the power matrix in South Asia had changed. If Pakistan has nuclear capability, it should come out with it.⁶

Nuclear explosions followed by provocative statements by the top BJP leadership were alarming. Perhaps Pakistan was left with no other option but to respond appropriately to the nuclear challenge. Pakistan did so to prevent India from adopting the strategy of hot pursuit against the freedom fighters in AJK. Pakistan's show of force prevented India from launching an offensive in Kashmir, and nuclear optimists generally believed that the overt nuclearisation of South Asia would significantly reduce the chances of an all-out war between India and Pakistan.

However, South Asia is unique in its understanding and pronouncements of nuclear deterrence. The enduring rivalry between India and Pakistan has transformed over the decades and attained a status of extremely complex conflict, unfortunately referred to as a nuclear flashpoint. Interestingly, the established world powers treat their atomic capabilities with extreme care and avoid making serious statements or adopting threatening postures against other states. However, when it comes to South Asia, nuclear weapons are considered like any other weapons. The presence of atomic weapons in the inventory of India and Pakistan has failed to deter wars and conflicts

between the two states in different forms and characters. The leadership of the two states do not miss an opportunity to blame each other for gross interference in their respective domestic affairs.

While India relies more on its conventional arms strengths, it promises the use of nuclear weapons in retaliation for a nuclear attack on its territory or its forces anywhere in the world. However, Pakistan maintains that it will not hesitate to use nuclear first if the situation so demands. Perhaps Pakistan would not wait to be reduced to half its conventional strength before atomic posturing. India would be more than happy to announce a ceasefire at that stage and declare itself a winner in the traditional phase of war, and yet be known as a state which saves humanity from the devastation of a nuclear war. Should that happen in any future war between India and Pakistan, rest assured that the fate of J&K would be sealed forever.

Pakistan's military establishment is fully aware of such a scenario, even if political leadership does not appreciate this. Therefore, the probability of an early interface of non-strategic nuclear weapons is exceedingly high without too much consideration of the consequences. Pakistan's present politico-military leadership appears quite resolute in their pronouncements and actions to respond to India's aggression, and the same was demonstrated by PAF on February 27, 2019, as well as on May 7, 2025.

Narrative of Events (February 2019 and May 2025)

India has mastered the art of state management to create a narrative and stage an unfortunate incident against its people to malign Pakistan, primarily as a *raison d'être* to attack its archrival. Without going into the details of earlier incidents of the Attack on the Indian Parliament in November 2001, and the Mumbai 2008, this paper will focus on two incidents of the recent past in February 2019 and May 2025.

Pulwama Incident leading to Balakot Strikes.

As the narrative goes, on February 14, 2019, a Kashmiri youngster carried out a suicide bombing near Pulwama, killing at least 46 Indian soldiers who were travelling in multiple military vehicles. Pakistan condemned that attack and helped in the investigation process. However, India immediately launched an aggressive exterior manoeuvre to

malign Pakistan for the subject attack on the Indian convoy, in a similar manner as was done following the attack on the Indian Parliament in 2001, and the Mumbai attacks of 2008.

While Indian diplomats were busy getting the nod from the Western capitals, the IAF was quietly preparing for strategic strikes against the alleged terror camps inside Pakistan. Concerned due to the Indian leadership's war rhetoric, Pakistan issued a stern warning that it will not think but retaliate to India's misadventures. However, India did not take Pakistan's warning seriously and defied the Cold War dictum that nuclear states do not go to war with each other, perhaps, because this is how it had planned.

IAF carried out a strike in the general area of Balakot on the night of February 26, 2019. India claimed that it had neutralised a terrorist training camp in the area, killing almost 300 terrorists, but failed to provide any evidence and could not prove its claim. Major media Houses made headlines like "India says it launched air strikes against militants in Pakistani territory, in a major escalation of tensions between the two countries."^{vii} However, Pakistan hosted international journalists to the affected area and showed them there were no camps there and only a few trees were destroyed by the IAF strike.

PAF successfully responded to IAF strikes the very next day, and that too in broad daylight. PAF not only launched standoff strikes in the proximity of the Indian Army's sensitive targets but also shot down two IAF fighter jets in the process. One of the pilots, Wing Commander Abhinandan, whose aircraft was shot down, but he ejected and safely landed inside Pakistan's part of Azad Kashmir (Independent Kashmir). However, Pakistan's behaviour was that of a sober state, and it did not glorify the capture of an IAF pilot and handed him over to the Indian authorities within days, only after necessary documentation. Pakistan's gesture was applauded worldwide and helped in strengthening its narrative that it wants peace and not a military conflict. While two IAF's fighter jets were shot down by the PAF, one of its "Mi-17 V5 helicopters crashed near Budgam, J&K. All six air warriors on board the helicopter suffered fatal injuries."^{viii} PAF did not claim

the Helicopter but insisted that it was shot down by the IAF's ground defences in the fog of war.

No matter how limited this aerial engagement was, it remains the first of its kind between two regular air forces of the two nuclear states. Hence, it immediately attracted the attention of major powers, who called for restraint from both sides. Since Pakistan was only responding to Indian attacks, it reacted positively and released the Indian pilot without any delay to ensure that the conflict did not escalate.

Pahalgam Incident Leading to Operation Sindoor

Since the Balakot response by the PAF, the IAF was preparing for a possible showdown to erase the memory of the humiliation it suffered on February 27, 2019. IAF successfully inducted S-400 Air defence Systems, operationalised French Rafale aircraft, and acquired several Killer drones from Israel. It may be worth noting that in an election rally in 2019, India's Prime Minister Modi stated that if the IAF had Rafale, it would have performed better.

India repeated the story of February 2019, but this time in the tourist resort of Pahalgam on April 22, 2025, located in the Occupied J&K.^{ix} Unfortunately, some 26 innocent tourists were killed in yet another stage-managed incident. The old script was being repeated as India launched an effective exterior manoeuvre to gain support from the Western Capitals. Pakistan once again condemned the attack and offered to cooperate in the investigations. However, India was not interested as it started to prepare for kinetic application, and once again led by the IAF. Soon after this unfortunate incident, this author wrote that "the possibility of yet another military engagement between India and Pakistan, like February 2019, exists with varying degrees of probability, thus challenging the efficacy of nuclear deterrence. Until the probabilities of military engagements are minimised, the possibilities of peace and stability in the region would remain elusive."^x

IAF took some two weeks to prepare to launch brazen attacks on Pakistan under the pretext of destroying the terror networks inside Pakistan, which were allegedly involved in the Pahalgam incident. Pakistan was prepared this time because it was a repeat of the February 2019 script.

On the night of 6th and 7th May, India launched multiple missile attacks in Azad Jammu & Kashmir

(AJK), Sialkot region across the Working Boundary, and deep inside Pakistan across international borders in Bahawalpur and Muridke areas. India codenamed it as 'Operation Sindoor.' While Indian strikes in AJK did not come as a surprise, attacks across the international boundary, so deep inside Pakistan's territory, may have surprised many. Most of these attacks were made on the mosques and madrasas to show the world that these were training centres of terror outfits. However, India's attacks on the Neelum-Jhelum Hydro Project are a serious attempt to sabotage Pakistan's efforts at water security and had to be treated as an act of war. IAF's multiple strikes on Pakistan's counterforce and countervalue targets could not be ignored, and therefore, Pakistan's response to India's brazen attacks was swift and deadly, naming it as 'Bunyanum Marsoos.'

PAF responded in kind and claimed to have shot down several IAF fighter jets patrolling inside Indian Occupied J&K. Some of the claims have been verified by Indian media and military officials. In contrast, international sources have also confirmed a few. The French-built Rafale aircraft suffered the most as the PAF claimed to have shot down at least three of them on the fateful night. However, the claims and counterclaims are part of aerial warfare and will only be confirmed much later. Pakistan Army has also claimed to have destroyed a Brigade HQ in the zone of operations.

This all happened on the night of 6th and 7th May; however, Indian attacks continued during the following days and nights. In the early hours of 8th May, various parts of Lahore were attacked by drones, only to be shot and captured by Pakistan Army's air defence units. The Modi-madness continued until 10th May, when Pakistan responded with full might to attack India's counterforce targets. Once India suffered a blow to its much-revered S-400 Air Defence Systems, only then did all sides agree to the ceasefire, which US President Donald Trump announced. Since Pakistan did not initiate the war, nor was it interested in escalation, it decided to propose a truce, and the ceasefire came into effect by evening on May 10, 2025.

While the IAF may have initiated the operations to avenge its losses suffered in February 2019, it ultimately incurred significantly more losses than it had incurred previously. PAF versus IAF aerial kills

score now stands at 10-0 in favour of the PAF, in the two limited aerial wars of the 21st Century.

India's Motives for Strategic Instability in South Asia

A close examination of India's motives to initiate such a short military engagement reveals that the country's leadership had political objectives. India was due for general elections, and perhaps Prime Minister Modi needed to build a narrative around Pakistan's support to terror outfits operating inside India's part of J&K. He successfully sold this narrative to the domestic audience and won the elections with a two-thirds majority needed to amend the Constitution of India. Modi did so immediately and abrogated the Constitution's Articles 370 and 35A, which gave special status to the Occupied Jammu and Kashmir. India's leadership feels emboldened by its actions and is now openly threatening to annex by force Pakistan's part of Azad Kashmir. India has released the new maps of its political boundaries showing Pakistan's Azad Kashmir and Gilgit-Baltistan as its Union Territories.^{xi}

For some time, India had relegated Pakistan to a mediocre state, which did not warrant much attention, and instead concentrated more on its preparations to counter China's rise. India was able to sell the challenge to China due to its proactive diplomacy and the influence of its diaspora. There is little doubt that the Indian diaspora has a highly influential presence worldwide, particularly in the United States and the United Kingdom.

India used the China card intelligently and convinced the global leaders that Pakistan does not matter to it anymore. It can challenge China if political and military support is extended to it. The idea of handling China's rise by India sounded great in the Western Capitals, and they readily extended unconditional political and military support to India. India felt emboldened and embarked on an ambitious military modernisation plan that included a range of hardware from various suppliers. India acquired state-of-the-art air defence systems, including the S-400 from Russia, the Dassault Rafale fighter aircraft from France, and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), as well as the Heron Mk2 and Harop drones from Israel, among others. From the US, India had already concluded multiple foundational agreements, including the Logistics Exchange Memorandum of

Agreement (LEMOA) and the Communications Compatibility and Security Agreement (COMCASA), which marked a significant step in strengthening military cooperation between the two countries, forming a 'troika of foundational pacts.' The lengthy negotiations following the foundational agreements culminated in the signing of the Basic Exchange and Cooperation Agreement (BECA) between India and the United States on October 27, 2020. BECA assured India of real-time intelligence and targeting information.^{xii}

With so many arms, ammunition, and equipment, India started to claim itself a regional power, relegated Pakistan to the minor opponent, and began to challenge China's power in the region. China, on the other hand, disregarded India as a major opponent and eyed a shift in the international system from unipolarity to multipolarity, with the solid support of Russia, another global power that had consolidated its position.

India's motives for ensuring strategic instability in South Asia are more closely tied to its domestic politics. Perhaps, PM Modi gains his domestic ratings for regional elections by waging wars with Pakistan. The more hatred Modi creates among the Indians against Pakistan, the more votes he gets from its hardline constituencies. This author opines that India will not let Pakistan be at peace because it wants to keep the terrorism narrative alive at both levels, international and domestic.

Pakistan's Response to India's Military Adventurism

Pakistan's response to India's aggression on both occasions, February 2019 and May 2025, was that of a sober state. On the political front, it offered help in free and fair investigations each time; however, India refused for obvious reasons. On the diplomatic front, Pakistan has consistently responded to calls for restraint and ceasefire by international players, particularly the US. Moreover, Pakistan voluntarily handed over the captured pilot, Wing Commander Abhinandan, to India to show grace and humility.

On the military front, too, Pakistan put up a measured response and did not go for the overkill even if it had the opportunity on multiple occasions, primarily because it did not want an escalation. India does not reciprocate Pakistan's gestures of goodwill, perhaps considering them a weakness. However, one thing is

of grave concern: India has made it incumbent upon Pakistan to maintain strategic stability every time it intends to destabilise it. Moreover, this author is very concerned about the aspect of stolen initiative. India has stolen the initiative from Pakistan, and it now dictates when to stage-manage the incident, when to start military operations, and when to effect a ceasefire. This should not have happened.

Conclusion

The situation in South Asia remains uncertain because the two neighbours do not have usual diplomatic relations and make no effort towards the process of conflict resolution. Two air wars, though limited, within the space of six years between two nuclear powers with a history of protracted conflicts, cannot be ignored.

The states that do not have conflicts with the neighbouring states deploy diplomacy and deterrence (D2) for the development and well-being of their people. In contrast, the states that have protracted disputes with neighbouring states employ it to ensure their territorial integrity and sovereignty. Interestingly, the application of both these concepts requires skilful employment to draw maximum benefits to accomplish the interests of the states. The states can avoid conflicts if both diplomacy and deterrence are working. However, if at least one is working, the conflict can be managed, but if both fail, a violent conflict may become unavoidable. Both

these concepts date back to times immemorial. However, each state has differing mechanisms for employing these concepts in different sets of circumstances. This author opines that the consequences of the failure of diplomacy and deterrence dilution may lead to violent conflicts that will only bring deaths, destruction, and devastation, particularly for small states. Therefore, it is incumbent upon states, particularly smaller states, to continue working on D2.

This author opines that the people of India and Pakistan deserve a better life, one that is peaceful and prosperous. Likewise, people of J&K have had a very rough time struggling for their demands of self-determination, which were promised to them by the UN in 1948. The two nuclear neighbours have had numerous limited wars under the nuclear overhang. On each occasion, it was the US which came to defuse tension and virtually separated its armed forces from the warfronts. However, the same may not happen during the next conflict and crisis because priorities change and unforeseen events occur. Therefore, it is strongly recommended that academia debate the situation in South Asia and impress upon the leadership of the two nuclear neighbours to engage in negotiations and resolve their disputes, rather than merely managing them. Because another military engagement between India and Pakistan, like that of February 2019 or May 2025, cannot be ruled out, no matter how limited it is.

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